

STUDYING THE PURPOSE AND FUNCTION OF CHILD PSYCHOLOGY**Karimbergenova Eleonora Sultan qizi**

Student of Karakalpak State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15368255>

Abstract. *This study presents the spiritual concept of child psychology, the process of a child's psychological development, how much attention a child needs, and the main concepts currently focused on raising children. The importance of psychology in raising children is very great. Information is provided that, in order for children to receive education, they must first pay attention to the state of psychological development.*

Keywords: *Child psychology, psychological development, psychological research, psyche, mental development.*

BOLALAR PSIXOLOGIYASINING MAQSADI VA VAZIFASINI O'RGANISH

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqotda bolalar psixologiyasining ma'naviy tushinchasi, bolani psixik rivojlanish jarayoni, bolaga e'tibor qanchalar kerakligi, hozirgi paytda bolalarni tarbiyasiga asosiy e'tiborini qaratishda asosiy tushunchalar keltirib o'tilgan. Bola tarbiyasida psixologiyaning ahamiyati juda katta. Bolalar ta'lim olishi uchun eng avvalo psixologik rivojlanish holatiga e'tibor qaratishi lozimligi haqida ma'lumotlar beriladi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Bolalar psixologiyasi, psixologik rivojlanish, psixologik tadqiqotlar, psixika, aqliy rivojlanish.*

Introduction

In the study of the age-appropriate development of children, psychologists face another important task: to develop methods for examining the development of the psyche of children, methods for determining their age-specific characteristics. Each discipline uses several methods, depending on the content of its subject. The search for the necessary facts, the identification and proof of the causes of their occurrence are carried out using scientific investigation methods. It should be emphasized that the only method of all sciences is the methodology of dialectical materialism. The specific methods of all sciences are based on this methodology. Child psychology, which studies the laws of children's mental life, is also based on the methodology of dialectical materialism and considers the true essence of subtle psychological phenomena, which are much more difficult to study than other phenomena, to be something that can be learned on a scientific basis. Child psychology, based on the principles of dialectical materialism, studies subjective phenomena consisting of complex

reflections together with their objective causes, that is, the physiological processes in the brain, which is the most complex type of living matter, and the entire psyche of a person, the material basis of society reflected in his consciousness, and the concrete socio-economic relations in it. The development of the child's psyche is an extremely complex and contradictory process. As in any other development, quantitative changes lead to qualitative changes, transitions, "leaps". For example, the gradual increase in a child's vocabulary leads to the acquisition of the grammatical structure of the language, and the repeated repetition of certain actions and behaviors ends with the formation of certain skills, habits, fixed characteristics in the individual. The most general laws of the development of the child's psyche include, firstly, the integration of consistency, that is, the integration of the child's initial scattered mental states into stable mental qualities of the individual, individual views on certain phenomena into a holistic worldview; secondly, the uneven development of certain processes, functions and qualities in the child's personality; thirdly, plasticity, which ensures the compensation of the shortcomings of some functions by other functions. The integration of the child's psyche is clearly manifested, for example, in the formation of observation based on the full perception of individual objects and phenomena, diligence based on the loving fulfillment of certain work tasks. Uneven development of the psyche can occur at all stages of life. For example, speech, especially in preschool age, interest in knowledge in adolescence, logical thinking in early adolescence, etc., develops rapidly. According to the findings of a number of psychologists, the main internal driving forces in the development of the child's psyche are primarily the following. During the development of the emotional sphere of preschool children, the relationship between the subject and the object that evokes emotional experiences is separated. The dynamic and substantive aspects of emotions and feelings in preschool age develop. The development of a child's emotions is associated with specific social situations. The child's understanding of the situation, experiencing the situation and changes in it creates a specific emotional state. In children, the delay may outweigh the braking. The child cannot restrain the vigorous expression of positive emotions, which can lead to the appearance of contradictory emotions. For example, a child's intense joy often ends in tears. In preschool age, the temporal structure of the child's activity gradually changes the place occupied by emotions: in the early stages, emotions are expressed as an emotional assessment of the achieved result, while in the later stages they are expressed as an emotional perception before the action is performed. If we turn to child psychology. The search for more effective methods of studying child psychology means developing methods that will serve to

obtain more accurate information about the specific features of children's mental development. Child psychology is a separate branch of psychology that studies the laws of children's mental development at different age periods, as well as the laws of transition from one age stage to another. Mental development is the passage of age periods from birth and the improvement of mental activity. Mental development consists of the process of the child's assimilation of knowledge and experience accumulated throughout human history and his formation as a person. At each stage of mental development, certain physiological and psychological changes are observed in the individual. Psychological age, reflecting the level of mental development of a person, is often called mental age. Types of mental age are determined on the basis of special test tasks designed for people of that age. The child perceives the world and the environment through the eyes of his parents. Whatever is bad for the parents, the child considers bad. Whoever the parents like, that person is good for the child. This situation continues until the child is 10-12 years old. After that, the child begins to learn to draw conclusions for himself. Therefore, every action of the child is your reflection in the mirror. When studying the child's psyche, the researcher must rely on a number of principles - rules, and adhere to them. These principles are as follows: The principle of objectivity requires the researcher not to confuse data with their interpretation. Child psychology is currently developing. The development of the science of child psychology is proceeding in two main directions: the theoretical solution of problems of the sources of mental development and the search for more effective methods of studying the child's psyche. By the theoretical solution of problems of the sources of mental development, we mean the views of representatives of the main psychological schools and directions on this problem. Child psychology studies the emergence and development of mental processes in children (cognitive, speech, emotional, volitional, etc.), the determination of mental properties, the development of various activities (games, study, work), and the formation of the child as a personality. Child psychology uses research methods developed in general psychology, but its application has its own unique characteristics. In the study of the age characteristics of a child's personality, studies called cross-sectional, cross-sectional and longitudinal are conducted. In the first case, a single mental process is studied simultaneously in children belonging to different age groups. In the second case (longitudinal), the mental characteristics of a certain (separately selected) child are studied over many years. This, in turn, makes it possible to observe the general course of their mental development. In child psychology, parents are mainly responsible for making the child feel their trust, respect, support, and

attention. Possible and impossible situations are taught. He cannot correctly perceive things in the outside world. In the development of his psychology, we should pay attention to the development of psychological cognitive processes such as memory, perception, thinking, speech, and attention. To prepare children psychologically for education, play psychological games with them. To develop their attention, play games that attract attention, and to develop their memory, use various pictures. Arranging pictures in a row also helps develop memory, attention, and thinking. Counting from numbers also has a positive effect on the psychological development of a child. There are several methods in psychology to determine the processes of memory, attention, and cognition in a child's development.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that childhood is of great importance in the way a person lives and the perfection of his life after birth. Because childhood is important for a person to receive education in school, develop equally with his peers, and be aware of the events happening in the outside world. If a child is not well cared for and fed properly after birth, until he reaches adulthood, the child will lag behind his peers psychologically and physiologically.

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